

THE EFFECT OF REWARDS AND PUNISHMENT ON WORK MOTIVATION OF PERMANENT EMPLOYEES IN A PALM OIL MILL

Yael Febrian Purba*¹, Yose Andre Sinuhaji²

¹Department of Plantation Product Processing Technology, Institut Teknologi Sawit Indonesia, Medan

²Department of Agribusiness, Institut Teknologi Sawit Indonesia, Medan

E-mail: yaelpurba27@gmail.com*¹, sinuhaji.4@gmail.com²

Received : 10 May 2026

Accepted : 06 June 2026

Revised : 16 May 2026

Published : 16 June 2026

Abstract

Rewards and punishments are important aspects of Human Resource management that directly influence employee work motivation. In the palm oil mill industry, where productivity and work efficiency significantly influence operational success, understanding the impact of rewards and punishments on employee work motivation is crucial. Motivation is a psychological drive that drives a person to take action to achieve a specific goal. Motivation involves desires, needs, or goals that drive a person's behavior, both consciously and unconsciously. This research was conducted at the PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 palm oil mill from October 2025 to January 2026, with the aim to determine the effect of rewards and punishments on the work motivation of process employees in the palm oil mill. This research used a quantitative descriptive method, and the population and sample consisted of 43 process employees, both shift 1 and shift 2. Data processing used SPSS version 22 software and testing included validity and reliability tests, classical assumption tests, and multiple linear regression analysis. Based on simultaneous testing, the F-count value is 4.417 with a significance level of 0.018, while the F-table is 3.23. Thus, F-count > F-table, it can be concluded that rewards and punishments significantly influence the work motivation of PKS employees. PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2.

Keywords: Reward, punishment, motivation, palm oil mill.

INTRODUCTION

The palm oil industry plays a crucial role in both global and national economic contexts. As a key agricultural commodity, palm oil and its products contribute to various aspects of daily life, from food consumption and personal care products to renewable energy sources. Indonesia, with its abundant natural resources, is known as one of the world's largest producers and exporters of palm oil. This sector not only contributes significantly to state revenue and economic growth but also provides livelihoods for millions of farmers and workers across various regions. The development of this industry is inseparable from the role of competent and qualified Human Resources (HR), as the industry's sustainability and competitiveness depend heavily on the capacity and motivation of its workers. A company's success in achieving its goals depends on the quality of its human resources, which are the most important component (Wahyuni et al., 2023).

Motivation is the psychological drive that drives a person to take action to achieve a specific goal. Motivation involves desires, needs, or goals that drive a person's behavior, both consciously and unconsciously. Motivation comes from the Latin *movere*, meaning to push or move (Rulianti & Nurpribadi, 2023). Companies need to address employee motivation by observing, supervising, changing, and directing employee behavior in line with the company's desired goals. Changes in energy within a person, characterized by the emergence of feelings and beginning with a response to goals, are known as motivation (Febrina & Rahmat, 2024). Motivation at work will be the foundation for someone to organize and succeed. Motivation is a process that drives people to engage in activities to achieve goals. If a person's goals in life are achieved, they will feel satisfied. An employee tends to have high work motivation when they receive strong support from their surroundings and from within themselves, which aims to improve their well-being. Support from those around them and the environment can encourage individuals to be more active in their work and achieve predetermined targets (Laksmi & Budiani, 2015). Work enthusiasm can also be seen from work motivation, which means the need to encourage and strive to achieve company goals. Many performance factors, such as culture and family, societal perceptions, gender, recognition and achievement, goals or aspirations, educational skills, and employee status, can influence an employee's motivation to work (Hana et al.,

2023). High motivation will improve employee performance. Good employees are responsible and willing to take risks at work. A company's success or failure is closely tied to employee performance. A safe, healthy, and productive work environment is crucial to maintaining employee motivation and comfort as they carry out their duties. Good workplace conditions significantly influence employee development.

Motivation can also be influenced by the compensation a company provides to employees, which will drive their performance. A remuneration system is a system for paying employees monthly compensation. The remuneration system must be restructured into a performance-based salary system. The remuneration system can be seen as a means of providing financial benefits, tangible benefits, and employee rights. It is also a key element of an employment relationship. It is the totality of financial and non-financial rewards for employees in exchange for their work or services (Darmawan et al., 2021). According to Hermingsih and Purwanti (2020), compensation is closely related to employee job satisfaction because it serves as a reward or feedback mechanism for measuring job satisfaction and employee performance. In general, compensation aims to benefit the company, the government, employees, and the community. Compensation programs should be established in accordance with fairness and applicable laws, while ensuring internal and external consistency. Compensation can be categorized into two large groups, namely: (1) Direct compensation means a reward given by the company to employees for their achievements, for the benefit of the company. Compensation can be given directly, for example, in the form of wages or salaries, incentives or bonuses, and position allowances. (2) Indirect compensation is the provision of compensation to employees as an addition based on management policy in order to improve employee welfare. Uncertain compensation is directly related to the work performed by employees, for example: holiday allowances, pension benefits, and health benefits.

The remuneration system is crucial in human resource management, as it directly influences employee motivation. In the palm oil mill industry, where productivity and work efficiency significantly influence operational success, understanding the impact of rewards and punishments on employee work motivation is crucial. Permanent employees, both classified as part of the group, have different roles within the organizational structure. Classified employees generally receive better facilities and incentives. This difference can affect the motivation and job satisfaction of each group. High employee work motivation is expected to increase productivity, reduce absenteeism, and decrease employee turnover. Therefore, it is important to analyze how the remuneration system implemented in palm oil mills affects the work motivation of these two employee groups. Based on the above description, the author is interested in researching the effect of rewards and punishments on employee work motivation, particularly permanent part-time employees in palm oil mills. This is done to determine how much influence rewards and punishments will have on employee work enthusiasm, thereby spurring employee performance.

METHOD

Research Design

This research was conducted at the PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2, from November 2025 to January 2026. This research falls under the quantitative descriptive research category. According to Susanto et al. (2024), quantitative research is a type of research in which hypotheses are tested, conclusions are drawn, and how variables interact with one another is understood. Quantitative descriptive research describes frequently occurring events or incidents using data analysis. This research method is used to examine specific populations and samples. This aligns with the process the researcher will undertake, namely, collecting data through questionnaires, observations, and interviews. The collected data will then be processed into figures that will demonstrate the impact of remuneration on the work motivation of non-class permanent employees and class permanent employees.

Data Analysis

The obtained data were analyzed quantitatively using SPSS statistical software version 22, including validity and reliability tests, classical assumption tests, multiple linear regression analysis, T-tests, F-tests, and determination of the determinant coefficient (R).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill was established in 2011, initially without a palm oil mill. Subur Arum Makmur-2 covers an area of 14 divisions with a total area of 1,000 hectares per division. The raw material for fresh fruit bunches comes from Fangiono Agro Plantation (FAP), Raka plantation, and BSP. Subur Arum Makmur-2 is a business unit owned by the First Resources Group, which operates in the palm oil agribusiness sector. First Resources Group is a palm oil company founded in Singapore in 1992 by the Fangiono family.

Respondent’s Identity Characteristics

Based on gender, all respondents were male employees (43 respondents), as Subur Arum Makmur-2 Company requires only men as employees at its palm oil mill (processing unit). Processing work requires extra energy that is generally beyond men's capabilities. Therefore, the Subur Arum Makmur-2 Palm Oil Mill Company chooses men as process employees because they have greater physical strength to perform the processing. Based on age, the characteristics of the respondents' identities are summarized in Table 1. The largest number of respondents were aged 38-47 years, accounting for 44%. Meanwhile, there were two smaller groups of respondents, namely those aged 18-27 years and >48 years, each at 9.5%. In this case, the age of the youngest and oldest employees did not hinder their work motivation.

Based on their level of education, as shown in Table 2, the majority of respondents were high school/vocational school/Islamic high school graduates (99%). In comparison, the remainder were junior high school graduates (1%). Their level of education does not determine employee work motivation. Finally, based on work length, the largest number of respondents were workers with 6-15 years of service (80%), while the fewest were workers with >25 years of service (2%).

Descriptive Analysis on Each Variables

Table 1 presents a breakdown of respondents' responses on the influence of rewards on work motivation. Process employees at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill experience a relatively high level of reward, with an average questionnaire response rate of 79%. It indicates that reward indicators, including salary/wages, bonuses, awards, and self-development, can increase employee work motivation. The highest level of reward received and perceived by process employees at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill is in the bonus and self-development indicators, with statements such as "the bonus makes me more enthusiastic about my work" and "the company gives me opportunities to attend training and seminars." In this regard, process employees are considered to have a very high work ethic, driven by the various awards given by the company, which positively influence their performance.

Table 1. Tabulation of respondents' answers for the reward variable

Question(s)	Note					Item Score	Total Score	Percentage	Category
	SA	A	SD	D	StD				
1	60	112	6	0	1	179	215	83%	Very high
2	20	84	54	0	0	158	215	73%	High
3	170	36	0	0	0	206	215	96%	Very high
4	0	4	57	34	6	101	215	47%	Low
5	60	112	6	0	1	179	215	83%	Very high
6	60	112	6	0	1	179	215	83%	Very high
7	170	36	0	0	0	206	215	96%	Very high
8	15	84	54	20	0	158	215	73%	High
Average						170.75	215	79%	High

Note: SA: Strongly agree; A: Agree; SD: Somewhat disagree; D: Disagree; StD: Strongly disagree

Table 2 summarizes respondents' responses regarding the effect of punishment on work motivation. Process employees at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill experienced a relatively high level of punishment, with an average response rate of 77%. It indicates that the punishment indicator, which comprises light, moderate, and severe punishments, can increase employee motivation. The highest level of punishment received and perceived by process employees at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill was the severe punishment indicator, which stated, "Termination of employment is a serious violation and cannot be tolerated by the company." In this regard, process employees are considered to have a strong sense of responsibility, which prevents them from treating their work arbitrarily and maintains their motivation, similar to receiving rewards from the company.

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Table 2. Tabulation of respondents' answers for the punishment variable

Question(s)	Note					Item Score	Total Score	Percentage	Category
	SA	A	SD	D	StD				
1	20	84	54	0	0	158	215	73%	High
2	20	84	54	0	0	158	215	73%	High
3	60	112	6	0	1	179	215	83%	Very high
4	0	28	93	10	0	131	215	61%	High
5	0	60	78	4	0	142	215	66%	High
6	40	140	0	0	0	180	215	84%	Very high
7	75	104	6	0	0	185	215	86%	Very high
8	90	88	9	0	0	187	215	87%	Very high
Average						165	215	77%	High

Note: SA: Strongly agree; A: Agree; SD: Somewhat disagree; D: Disagree; StD: Strongly disagree

Table 3 summarizes respondents' responses to work motivation parameters. Process employees at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill has relatively high work motivation, with an average questionnaire response rate of 80%. This indicates that work motivation indicators, consisting of physiological needs, responsibility, security, social needs, recognition, self-actualization, and work ethic, can increase employee motivation. The highest level of work motivation is perceived by process employees at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill is in the work safety indicator, which states, "The company has a clear and well-implemented work safety policy." In this case, process employees need not worry about the company's safety guarantees as long as they adhere to the mill's standard operating procedures, thereby maintaining employee motivation.

Table 3. Tabulation of respondents' answers for the work motivation variable

Question(s)	Note					Item Score	Total Score	Percentage	Category
	SA	A	SD	D	StD				
1	80	100	6	0	0	186	215	87%	Very high
2	75	104	6	0	0	185	215	73%	High
3	75	96	0	8	0	179	215	83%	Very high
4	130	64	3	0	0	197	215	92%	Very high
5	45	96	30	0	0	171	215	80%	Very high
6	0	4	57	34	6	101	215	47%	Low
7	130	64	3	0	0	197	215	92%	Very high
8	80	100	6	0	0	186	215	87%	Very high
Average						175.25	215	80%	Very high

Note: SA: Strongly agree; A: Agree; SD: Somewhat disagree; D: Disagree; StD: Strongly disagree

Statistical Analysis Results

Validity and Reliability Tests

The validity test aims to ensure the instrument (data collection tool) used in the study is valid by correlating each item score with the total item score. Instrument validity testing is conducted using the following criteria:

- If the calculated $r > \text{table } r$, then the statement is declared valid.
- If the calculated $r < \text{table } r$, then the statement is declared invalid.

The validity test results are shown in Table 4. Based on Table 4, the calculated r values for 8 statements in the reward variable (X1), 8 statements in the punishment variable (X2), and 8 statements in the work motivation variable (Y) are greater than the r_{table} , which is 0.300. Thus, all statements in the questionnaire for each variable are declared valid.

Table 4. Validity test results for reward, punishment, and work motivation of employee

Statement(s)	r _{count}	r _{table}	Note
Reward (X1)			
X1.1	0.745	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X1.2	0.560	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X1.3	0.580	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X1.4	0.364	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X1.5	0.745	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X1.6	0.745	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X1.7	0.580	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X1.8	0.560	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Punishment (X2)			
X2.1	0.709	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X2.2	0.435	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X2.3	0.427	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X2.4	0.710	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X2.5	0.482	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X2.6	0.343	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X2.7	0.710	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
X2.8	0.709	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Work motivation (Y)			
Y.1	0.709	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Y.2	0.435	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Y.3	0.427	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Y.4	0.710	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Y.5	0.482	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Y.6	0.343	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Y.7	0.710	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)
Y.8	0.709	0.300	r _{count} > r _{table} (Valid)

Source: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

The reliability test used Cronbach's Alpha, which assesses the consistency of the measuring instrument, even though the study was conducted repeatedly with the same instrument. Reliability testing is considered reliable (trustworthy) if Cronbach's Alpha is > 0.60. As shown in Table 5, the Cronbach's Alpha value for 24 statement items is greater than 0.60, indicating that the entire questionnaire is reliable. Thus, the reward, punishment, and work motivation are declared reliable (trustworthy).

Table 5. Reliability test results for X1, X2, dan Y variables

Variable(s)	Cronbach's Alpha	Total Item (n)	Note
Reward (X1)	0,747 > 0,60	8	Reliable
Punishment (X2)	0,652 > 0,60	8	Reliable
Work motivation (Y)	0,652 > 0,60	8	Reliable

Sources: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

Classical Assumption Test

1. Normality tests

Normality testing used the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistical test, the histogram approach, and the P-plot graphic approach. The results of the normality test are shown in Table 6, where the Asymp.sig.(2-tailed) value is $0.200 > \alpha (0.05)$. Therefore, the research data are normally distributed. Based on Figure 1, the data distribution is balanced and follows a bell-shaped pattern. Thus, the data are normally distributed. Furthermore, Figure 2 shows that the data points are spread out and follow the diagonal line, indicating the data are normally distributed.

Tabel 6. Normality test results
One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residual
N		43
Normal Parameters ^{a,b}	Mean	.0000000
	Std. Deviation	2.49924029
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.062
	Positive	.051
	Negative	-.062
Test Statistic		.062
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.200 ^{c,d}

- a. Test distribution is Normal.
 - b. Calculated from data.
 - c. Lilliefors Significance Correction.
 - d. This is a lower bound of the true significance.
- Source: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

Figure 1. Histogram test
 Source: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

Figure 2. P-plot of regression
 Source: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

2. Multicollinearity test

The multicollinearity test assesses whether the regression model shows strong correlation among the independent variables. Multicollinearity can be ruled out if the Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) are < 10 and the tolerance values are > 0.1. The results of the multicollinearity test in this study are shown in Table 7. Based on Table 10, the VIF and tolerance values do not indicate multicollinearity, as the VIF values for both variables, namely reward and punishment, are <10, and the tolerance values are > 0.1.

Tabel 7. Multicollinearity test results
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
1 (Constant)	15.682	5.806			2.701	.010		
REWARD	-.058	.169	-.065		-.343	.734	.577	1.734
PUNISHMENT	.611	.248	.464		2.465	.018	.577	1.734

a. Dependent Variable: WORK MOTIVATION

Source: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

3. Heteroscedasticity test

This heteroscedasticity test is performed using a scatter plot. If the pattern is regular, heteroscedasticity can be declared. Conversely, if the pattern is irregular and the points are scattered irregularly, heteroscedasticity cannot be declared. The results of the heteroscedasticity test using a scatter plot are shown in the following figure. Based on Figure 3, the points are randomly distributed and do not form a distinct pattern. Thus, this regression model does not experience heteroscedasticity.

Figure 3. Heteroscedasticity test
Source: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

Multiple Regression Analysis

The purpose of the multiple linear regression analysis is to determine the influence of the independent variables, namely reward and punishment, on the dependent variable, namely work motivation, at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill, and to determine the magnitude of the influence between the independent variables and the dependent variable. The results of the multiple linear regression analysis test can be seen in the Table 8.

Tabel 8. Multiple regression analysis results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	15.682	5.806		2.701	.010
REWARD	-.058	.169	-.065	-.343	.734
PUNISHMENT	.611	.248	.464	2.465	.018

a. Dependent Variable: WORK MOTIVATION

Sumber: Data was processed using SPSS (2026)

Based on Table 11, the constant is 15.682, with regression coefficients of 0.058 for the reward variable (X1) and 0.611 for the punishment variable (X2). So the regression equation can be obtained as follows:

$$Y = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2$$

$$Y = 15.682 - 0.058X_1 + 0.611X_2$$

The following conclusions can be drawn from the regression equation:

- The constant value of 15.682 indicates that the independent variables (reward, X1 and punishment, X2), are considered constant for the dependent variable (work motivation, Y). If the reward (X1) and punishment (X2) variables are 0 (zero) or constant, then the work motivation (Y) variable has a value of 15.682.
- The regression coefficient for the reward (X1) variable is -0.058, with a negative value indicating that each additional reward score will reduce employee work motivation by -0.058, assuming other variables remain constant.
- The regression coefficient for the punishment (X2) variable has a unidirectional and positive relationship with a coefficient value of 0.611. It indicates that when punishment (X2) increases, employee work motivation (Y) will increase as well.

Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing was conducted using the t-test and F-test. The purpose of the t-test is to determine the influence of one independent variable in explaining changes in the dependent variable. The following criteria can determine the t-test results:

- If the significance value is < 0.05 or the t_{count} is greater than the t_{table} , this means there is a partial significant effect between the independent variable (reward or punishment) and the dependent variable (work motivation).
- If the significance value is > 0.05 or the t_{count} is less than the t_{table} , this means there is no partial significant effect between the independent variable (reward or punishment) and the dependent variable (work motivation).

As summarized in Table 9, For the effect of rewards on employee work motivation, the t_{count} (-0.343) is < the t_{table} (2.021), with a significance level of 0.734 > 0.05. It can be concluded that reward does not affect employee work motivation. On the other hand, t-test of the effect of punishment on employee work motivation produces a t_{count} (2.465) > t_{table} (2.021), with a significance level of 0.018 < 0.05. Thus, punishment significantly affects employee work motivation.

Tabel 9. T-test results

Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	15.682	5.806		2.701	.010
REWARD	-.058	.169	-.065	-.343	.734
PUNISHMENT	.611	.248	.464	2.465	.018

a. Dependent Variable: WORK MOTIVATION

The F-test is conducted to determine whether the independent variables jointly have a significant effect on the dependent variable.

- If the sig value is < 0.05 , or the $F_{count} > F_{table}$, then there is a simultaneous effect of variable X on variable Y.
- If the sig value is > 0.05 , or the $F_{count} < F_{table}$, then there is no simultaneous effect of variable X on variable Y.

Based on Table 10, the F_{count} is 4.417 with a significance level of 0.018, while the F_{table} is 3.23 ($F_{count} > F_{table}$). Thus, it can be concluded that rewards and punishments significantly influence employee work motivation at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill.

Tabel 10. F-test results ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	57.939	2	28.969	4.417	.018 ^b
	Residual	262.340	40	6.559		
	Total	320.279	42			

a. Dependent Variable: MOTIVASI KERJA

b. Predictors: (Constant), PUNISHMENT, REWARD

Source: Data was processed using SPSS

Coefficient of Determination (R)

The coefficient of determination is used to quantify the proportion of variance in the dependent variable explained by the independent variable. It is used to determine the extent of the contribution or percentage of the influence of rewards and punishments on work motivation. The coefficient of determination is between 0 and 1. A value close to one proves that the independent variable provides almost all the information needed to predict the variation of the dependent variable. The results of the coefficient of determination test are shown in Table 11. The coefficient of determination obtained is 0.181. It means that 18.10% of the employee work motivation variable is determined by the two independent variables, namely reward and punishment. While the remaining 81.90% is influenced by other variables not studied.

Table 11. Determination test

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.425 ^a	.181	.140	2.561

a. Predictors: (Constant), PUNISHMENT, REWARD

b. Dependent Variable: WORK MOTIVATION

Source: Data was processed data using SPSS (2026)

The Effect of Reward on the Work Motivation of Employee

The partial test results for the reward variable show a t-count ($-0.343 < t\text{-table}$ (2.021), with a significance level of $0.734 > 0.05$. It means that rewards for some PKS employees. PT Subur Arum Makmur-2 are in the opposite direction to work motivation. Generally, rewarding employees for their work should have a positive impact on work motivation. However, when viewed from the responses of several respondents at PKS. PT Subur Arum Makmur-2: Some still believe that the company's rewards do not motivate employees in their work. It is because many employees have not met the target to receive company awards. Besides, some respondents believe that receiving rewards from the company, such as a monthly salary or bonus, is enough, and they assume that increasing work motivation is unnecessary if, in the end, all employees will receive the salary offered by the company. In fact, work motivation is very helpful in encouraging oneself to complete the work. This also aligns with research by Gunawan et al. (2023), which found that rewards have a positive, but not always significant, effect on employee work motivation. It means that the size of the rewards employees receive does not significantly affect their motivation to work.

The Effect of Punishment on the Work Motivation of Employee

Partial testing related to the effect of punishment on employee work motivation produces a t-count (2.465) which is greater than the t-table (2.021), with a significance level of $0.018 < 0.05$. Thus, it can be concluded that punishment significantly influences employee work motivation at PT Subur Arum Makmur-2 Mill. Punishment is a

negative or positive consequence imposed by the company on individuals in response to undesirable behavior, aiming to maintain employee discipline and foster a sense of responsibility for the work done.

The Effect of Reward and Punishment on the Work Motivation of Employee

Based on the simultaneous test, the calculated F-value was 4.417 with a significance level of 0.018, while the F-table value was 3.23. Thus, it can be concluded that rewards and punishments significantly influence employee work motivation at PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill. The coefficient of determination test yielded an R-square value of 0.181. It means that 18.10% of employee work motivation (Y) is determined by the two independent variables, namely reward (X1) and punishment (X2). The remaining 81.90% is influenced by other variables not examined. Motivation is the effort to generate encouragement or stimulation. When an employee carries out their work, a specific motivation underlies their actions. This motivation relates to the goals or desires the employee seeks to achieve. In general, employees work to meet economic needs, develop their potential, advance, and receive recognition for their efforts (Wardani & Hendratni, tt).

CONCLUSION

This study shows that rewards have a positive effect on work motivation, but not all are significant in the PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 mill. On the other hand, punishment has a positive and significant effect on work motivation. Punishment given to employees who violate can influence the level of work motivation. This finding is supported by the F test (F-count > F-table), which indicates a significant effect of rewards and punishment on the work motivation of PKS employees. PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2. The results of this study recommend that PT. Subur Arum Makmur-2 should pay more attention to employee motivation, especially by providing appropriate rewards based on the work results achieved by the employee.

REFERENCES

- Darmawan, D., Iriandha, D., Indrianto, D., Sigita, D. S., & Cahyani, D. (2021). *Hubungan Remunerasi, Retensi dan Kinerja Karyawan*. 1(4).
- Febrina, I., & Rahmat, H. K. (2024). Motivasi Kerja Sumber Daya Manusia dalam Organisasi: Sebuah Tinjauan Pustaka. *Journal of Current Research in Humanities, Social Sciences, and Business*, 1(1), 29–34. <https://doi.org/10.71383/Wbq52h63>
- Hana, H. S. P., Trirahayu, D., & Whisnu Hendratni, T. (2023). Pengaruh Stres Kerja dan Motivasi Kerja terhadap Produktivitas Kerja Karyawan pada PT Reasuransi Nasional Indonesia. *JIMP: Jurnal Ilmiah Manajemen Pancasila*, 3(1), 70–83. <https://doi.org/10.35814/Jimp.V3i1.3634>
- Hermingsih, A., & Purwanti, D. (2020). Pengaruh Kompensasi dan Beban Kerja terhadap Kepuasan Kerja dengan Motivasi Kerja sebagai Variabel Pemoderasi. *Jurnal Dimensi*, 9(3), 574–597. <https://doi.org/10.33373/Dms.V9i3.2734>
- Laksmi, K. K., & Budiani, M. S. (2015). Psychological Well Being dan Motivasi Kerja pada Pegawai Dinas Pendidikan. *Jurnal Psikologi Teori dan Terapan*, 6(1), 50. <https://doi.org/10.26740/Jptt.V6n1.P50-53>
- Rulianti, E., & Nurpribadi, G. (2023). Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja, Lingkungan Kerja dan Pengembangan Karir terhadap Kepuasan Kerja Karyawan. *Jesya*, 6(1), 849–858. <https://doi.org/10.36778/Jesya.V6i1.1011>
- Candra Susanto, P., Ulfah Arini, D., Yuntina, L., Panatap Soehaditama, J., & Nuraeni, N. (2024). Konsep Penelitian Kuantitatif: Populasi, Sampel, dan Analisis Data (Sebuah Tinjauan Pustaka). *Jurnal Ilmu Multidisplin*, 3(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.38035/Jim.V3i1.504>
- Wahyuni, R., Gani, A., & Syahnur, M. H. (T.T.). *Pengaruh Motivasi Kerja dan Lingkungan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan*
- Wardani, A. S., & Hendratni, T. W. (T.T.). *Pengaruh Motivasi dan Pengalaman Kerja terhadap Produktivitas Karyawan Pada PT. Reasuransi Nasional Indonesia*